

smother rice seedlings and pose a threat when transplanted into the main ricefield, resulting in increases in the cost of cultivation and decreases in grain yield.

We conducted field experiments during the kharif (wet season) and summer (dry) seasons for 2 yr (1993-94 to 1994-95) to find a suitable herbicide to control nursery weeds. The experiments were conducted at the Regional Research Station, Mudigere, in a randomized block design with four replications and seven treatments. The plot size was 1 m² with nurseries grown under both dry (raised) and wet (flat) beds. The soil was a red sandy loam with pH 5.2, 78% organic carbon, 7.5 kg P ha⁻¹ and 68 kg K ha⁻¹. Seeds of cultivar Intan were sown during the second week of June (wet season) and second week of December (dry season). Herbicides were applied within 24 h of sowing, except for Anilophos, which was applied 3 d after sowing. A common recommended basal dose of

Table 2. Seasonal dry weed weight (DWW) and weed control efficiency (WCE) in hill zone of Karnataka, India.

Treatment	1993-94				1994-95			
	Kharif		Summer		Kharif		Summer	
	DWW (g)	WCE (%) ^a	DWW (g)	WCE (%)	DWW (g)	WCE (%)	DWW (g)	WCE (%)
1	142.4	–	102.2	–	132.2	–	96.2	–
2	52.6	63	30.6	70	48.4	63	26.3	73
3	79.7	44	59.3	42	86.3	35	56.4	41
4	83.2	41	46.2	55	78.3	41	43.3	55
5	71.4	50	42.3	59	68.3	48	38.1	60
6	56.6	60	32.5	68	52.2	60	31.3	67
7	50.9	64	28.2	72	45.2	66	25.2	74
LSD (P = 0.05)	10.1	–	13.7	–	12.1	–	14.0	–

^aWCE = [Control WW – treatment WW] / control WW × 100.

90-45-45 kg NPK ha⁻¹ was applied before sowing.

Butachlor 50EC and Anilophos 30EC had no phytotoxic effect on rice. The germination percentage of rice was higher on Butachlor 50EC, Anilophos, hand weeding, and control plots (Table 1). Weed control efficiency, dry weight of seedlings, and seedling height were also higher for these treatments

compared with the control (Table 2). Better rice seedling growth was probably because of the weed-free environment and better use of available moisture, light, and applied nutrients. From an economic point of view, nursery weed control with effective herbicides cost \$1.83 (Rs 55) per 750 m² area of nursery—the area required for a 1-ha ricefield. ■

Weed control in dry-seeded lowland rice

R. Rajendran and N. Kempuchetty, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

Traditional growers of transplanted rice in the Cauvery new delta zone of Tamil Nadu State often switch to semidry rice culture because of the nonavailability of water and labor. Under semidry rice culture, premonsoon dry seeding is practiced and the rice crop is submerged after about a month. A major constraint in this type of rice cultivation is high weed incidence.

We therefore evaluated five weed control treatments involving two preemergence herbicides followed by hand weeding, one preemergence herbicide followed by a postemergence one, a postemergence herbicide followed by hand weeding, and two hand weeding during 1992 and 1994 in September to January (late samba season) in the Cauvery new delta zone.

One unweeded control plot was maintained separately to assess weed control efficiency (WCE). The dry seeds of ADT 38 (135 d duration) were sown on a dry field and submerged after 1 mo. The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

The soil was a sandy loam. Thiobencarb was applied 6 d after seeding (DAS), pretilachlor plus at 3 DAS, and

2,4-D Na salt and bentazon at 25 DAS. Plots treated with preemergence herbicides were hand weeded at 25 DAS and the bentazon-treated plot at 45 DAS. Plots with two hand weeding were weeded at 25 and 45 DAS.

The experimental fields were dominated by *Echinochloa colona* among grasses, *Cyperus rotundus* among sedges, and *Trianthema portulacastrum* among broadleaf weeds. In the weed

Effect of weed control on grain yield, weed dry weight, and weed control efficiency in dry-seeded lowland rice in the Cauvery new delta zone, Tamil Nadu, India, 1992 and 1994.

Treatment	Rate (kg ai ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Weed dry weight (t ha ⁻¹)			WCE ^a (%)		
		1992	1994	Mean	1992	1994	Mean	1992	1994	Mean
		Thiobencarb followed by 2,4-D Na salt	2.0 + 1.0	3.8	3.8	3.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	80.1
Thiobencarb followed by hand weeding	1.5	4.3	5.1	4.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	79.6	70.3	74.9
Pretilachlor plus followed by hand weeding	0.3	5.0	6.0	5.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	89.1	80.9	85.0
Bentazon followed by hand weeding	0.8	3.0	2.9	2.9	0.8	0.8	0.8	54.1	59.1	56.6
Two hand weeding	–	4.3	4.8	4.5	0.6	0.7	0.7	60.5	70.7	65.6
LSD (0.05)	–	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.08	0.05	–	–	–

^aMean of four replications.

control treatments, pretilachlor plus (0.3 kg ai ha⁻¹) with one hand weeding significantly reduced total weed dry weight at 60 DAS, with a maximum

WCE of 85%. This treatment also produced the best yield—5.49 t ha⁻¹ (see table). Thiobencarb (1.5 kg ai ha⁻¹) with one hand weeding was as effective as

two hand weedings. No post-emergence herbicide was as effective for dry-seeded lowland rice. ■

Research methodology

The relationship between experimental plot research and Texas rice producers' ratoon field results

T. N. Thompson, M. E. Rister, W. R. Grant, Department of Agricultural Economics, Texas A&M University, College Station, Texas 77843, USA; A. D. Klosterboer, G. N. McCauley, J. W. Stansel, Agricultural Research Center, Beaumont, Texas 77713, USA; J. P. Krausz, Department of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Texas A&M University; B. M. Drees, Department of Entomology; F. T. Turner, C. N. Bollich, M. A. Marchetti, M. O. Way, B. D. Webb, N. G. Whitney, S. R. M. Pinson, Agricultural Research Center, Beaumont, Texas; and C. R. Schubert, Department of Agricultural Economics, Texas A&M University

At several recent Texas (USA) rice industry meetings, rice consultants and producers mentioned observing input responses different from those reported by extension and research specialists. This study documents the correlation between scientists' recommendations based on existing theory drawn from rice plot research and actual results from commercial fields obtained from producers' surveys during 1987-89. Scientists' expert ex ante opinions on the effects of several predetermined, decision, and uncertain factors on ratoon crop rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) field yield and quality (milling yield, head yield, and grade) were documented. A modified Delphi procedure, whereby scientists come to a consensus agreement, was used to determine an extensive set of independent variables hypothesized to either positively or negatively affect ratoon crop yield and quality. The scientists' identified variables provided the basis for a mail survey of Texas rice producers' cultural practices and yield-quality responses

Summary statistics for the ratoon crop models, 1987-89 Texas ratoon crop survey.

Item	Ratoon crop models ^a			
	RY ^b	RYM ^c	RHY ^d	RG ^e
F value	9.8350	2.6570	2.5010	1.6730
Prob > F	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0047
R square	0.6397	0.3413	0.4057	0.0203
Adj R square	0.5746	0.2129	0.2898	0.0816
CV	1.6388	2.6347	5.2959	71.1072
Observations (no.)	413	381	381	380

^aEach model has approximately 40-50 variables that were hypothesized to affect yield and quality according to rice research and extension scientists. The variables include those that are (a) known at the beginning of the production period (predetermined variables such as soil type), (b) controlled by the decision maker within the production period (decision variables (such as fertilizer management), and (c) beyond the decision maker's control (uncertain variables, such as climate). ^bRY = ratoon crop yield. ^cRYM = ratoon crop milling yield. ^dRHY = ratoon crop head yield. ^eRG = ratoon crop grade.

during 1987-89. Following collection of the survey data, multiple regression procedures and associated statistical tests were used to identify statistically significant ratoon yield and quality-influencing variables.

Table presents summary regression results. The predetermined variables included management (3 variables), soils (2), water management (2), land preparation (4), and rotation (7). The decision variables were varieties (2), fertilization (10), emergence / seeding (3), water management (8), diseases (3), pests (4), and harvesting (10). The uncertainty variables consisted of weather (6) and diseases (2).

Low coefficients of determination indicate that the model formulations and the hypotheses identified for the ratoon crop yield and quality models do not fully account for the variability in actual ratoon crop field yields and quality. In many cases, scientists' hypotheses matched producers' ratoon yield and quality responses; however, sometimes the apparent direction of effect in

the data set was in an opposite direction than hypothesized. For example, 1988 was hypothesized to have been a more favorable year for ratoon field yields and quality. Statistical results indicate that the scientists' hypothesis of higher field yields was supported, but their hypothesis regarding higher quality (milling yield) was rejected.

Comparison of the number of statistically significant variables between the yield and quality models indicates that 42% of the scientists' hypothesized yield variables were significant, whereas 45% of the scientists' hypothesized quality variables were significant. Hypothesized signs for the statistically significant variables were then compared with calculated signs for alternative farm scenarios based on the regression results. Agreement with scientists' hypotheses occurs if the calculated sign is the same as the hypothesized sign. Such "in agreement" results suggest that scientists well recognize and understand the effect of these factors on Texas rice farmers' ratoon crop yields and quality. Comparison between the yield and quality models indicates that, for the yield model, 36% of the statistically significant hypotheses were in agreement, whereas 24% were in agreement for the quality models. In summary, scientists were less likely to determine the input impacts on quality rather than yield. These results indicate the importance of determining direct and interactive effects of production variables on rice quality.

The use of producer surveys provides opportunities for researchers to extensively evaluate numerous producer circumstances beyond the capability of experimental plot research and verification trials. This type of evalua-